

STRAINS OF ECCENTRIC COMPRESSED RC COLUMNS STRENGTHENED WITH CFRP MATERIALS

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SUMMARY

The subject of conducted experimental studies was analysis of influence of compressive force eccentricity on strains and effectiveness of strengthening of eccentric compressed reinforced concrete columns strengthened with CFRP strips and sheets.

Keywords: research, column, strain, strengthening, CFRP

INTRODUCTION

The results of the experimental studies of strains of eccentric compressed RC columns strengthened with CFRP sheets and strips will be shown in the paper.

The aim of the studies was to evaluate the influence of longitudinal CFRP reinforcement intensity and construction manner of transverse CFRP reinforcement on strain, strength and strengthening effectiveness of eccentric compressed RC columns strengthened with CFRP strips and sheets.

EXPERIMENTAL STUDY

The study was conducted on model specimens of columns of dimensions of 200x200 mm (in cross section) and 1500 mm (height).

In the studies maximum possible intensity of CFRP strengthening with one layer of strips was applied. The intensity of external reinforcement of columns is described with strengthening level ρ_L (area of longitudinal CFRP strips – A_L in relation to area of concrete cross section in element – A_c).

In order to achieve the objectives of the studies six specimens strengthened with CFRP materials specimens and three control specimens without strengthening were performed and tested.

The assumptions of the research program are as follows:

Variable parameters:

a) force eccentricity: A_1 – axial compression, A_2 – $h/12$, A_3 – $h/6$,

b) transverse external reinforcement:

B_1 – local transverse reinforcement (SikaWrap Hex 230C),

B_2 – single continuous reinforcement (S&P C Sheet 240),

Constant parameters:

c) modulus of elasticity of CFRP strips:

C_1 – 210 GPa (Sika CarboDur type M),
 C_2 – 200 GPa (S&P CFK-Lamellen 200/2000),

d) intensity of external reinforcement:

D_1 – 2,53%.

According to this parameters two kinds of strengthened elements were performed. These elements were subjected to immediate axial or eccentric compression (in accordance with specification in table).

Specimen type A:

Intensity of external reinforcement – 2,53%, strips Sika Carbodur type M, local transverse reinforcement made of sheet SikaWrap Hex 230C.

Specimen type B:

Intensity of external reinforcement – 2,53%, strips S&P CFK-Lamellen 200/2000, single continuous reinforcement S&P C Sheet 240.

Eccentricity	Axial compression	Eccentricity h/12	Eccentricity h/6
Type of specimens	<i>SwzA_0</i>	<i>SwzA_16</i>	<i>SwzA_32</i>
	<i>SwzB_0</i>	<i>SwzB_16</i>	<i>SwzB_32</i>

Figure 1. Specimens in investigative emplacement

References

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